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- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEADING WHEAT-PRODUCING COUNTRIES

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Abstract. This research examines the adoption of innovative agricultural technologies in the world's ten largest wheat-producing countries and analyzes their wheat production dynamics over the last five years (2019–2023). Using FAO and USDA official datasets, the study identifies production trends and evaluates the impact of digital agriculture, precision farming, remote-sensing monitoring, climate-resilient wheat varieties, and AI-based decision-making tools. Findings show that countries implementing advanced agro-technologies such as China, Russia, India, Australia, and France demonstrate higher production stability despite climate volatility. Conversely, countries with limited technological integration show significant fluctuations in output due to climate stress and environmental risks. The study concludes that innovative technologies play a decisive role in increasing productivity, ensuring resilience, and strengthening global food security.

Keywords: Wheat production; innovative technologies; digital agriculture; NDVI; precision farming; climate-smart agriculture; global producers.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot dunyoning eng yirik o'nta bug'doy yetishtiruvchi mamlakatlarida innovatsion qishloq xo'jaligi texnologiyalarini joriy etishni o'rganadi va so'nggi besh yil ichida (2019–2023) ularning bug'doy ishlab chiqarish dinamikasini tahlil qiladi. FAO va USDA rasmiy ma'lumotlar to'plamlaridan foydalangan holda, tadqiqot ishlab chiqarish tendentsiyalarini aniqlaydi va raqamli qishloq xo'jaligi, aniq dehqonchilik, masofadan zondlash monitoringi, iqlimga chidamli bug'doy navlari va sun'iy intellektga asoslangan qaror qabul qilish vositalarining ta'sirini baholaydi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, Xitoy, Rossiya, Hindiston, Avstraliya va Fransiya kabi ilg'or agrotexnologiyalarni joriy etuvchi mamlakatlar iqlim o'zgaruvchanligiga qaramay, yuqori ishlab chiqarish barqarorligini namoyish etadilar. Aksincha, texnologik integratsiyasi cheklangan mamlakatlar iqlim stressi va ekologik xavflar tufayli ishlab chiqarishda sezilarli tebranishlarni ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot innovatsion texnologiyalar unumdorlikni oshirish, barqarorlikni ta'minlash va global oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini mustahkamlashda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi degan xulosaga keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Bug'doy ishlab chiqarish; innovatsion texnologiyalar; raqamli qishloq xo'jaligi; NDVI; aniq dehqonchilik; iqlimga asoslangan qishloq xo'jaligi; global ishlab chiqaruvchilar.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматривается внедрение инновационных сельскохозяйственных технологий в десяти крупнейших странах мира – производителях пшеницы и анализируется динамика их производства за последние пять лет (2019–2023 гг.). Используя официальные данные ФАО и Министерства сельского хозяйства США, исследование выявляет тенденции производства и оценивает влияние цифрового сельского хозяйства, точного земледелия, дистанционного зондирования, климатоустойчивых сортов пшеницы и инструментов принятия решений на основе искусственного интеллекта. Результаты показывают, что страны, внедряющие передовые агротехнологии, такие как Китай, Россия, Индия, Австралия и Франция, демонстрируют более высокую стабильность производства, несмотря на изменчивость климата. Напротив, страны с ограниченной технологической интеграцией демонстрируют значительные колебания производства из-за климатического стресса и экологических рисков. В исследовании сделан вывод о том, что инновационные технологии играют решающую роль в повышении производительности, обеспечении устойчивости и укреплении глобальной продовольственной безопасности.

Ключевые слова: Производство пшеницы; инновационные технологии; цифровое сельское хозяйство; NDVI; точное земледелие; климатически оптимизированное сельское хозяйство; мировые производители.

INTRODUCTION

Wheat remains one of the world's most important staple crops, playing a strategic role in global food security. According to Goldman Sachs forecasts, the world population will reach 9.8 billion by 2050, requiring at least a 70% increase in food production. This growing demand places substantial pressure on wheat-producing countries to ensure stable and sustainable production despite climate change, land degradation, and environmental limitations. Over the last decade, the adoption of innovative technologies including satellite-based monitoring systems, AI-driven irrigation networks, genetically improved wheat varieties, drone spraying, and Big Data analytics has transformed global wheat production. Countries such as China, Russia, India, the United States, Canada, Australia, France, and Germany have synchronized agricultural modernization policies with digital transformation to increase yield stability and reduce vulnerability to climate shocks. This paper evaluates the five-year production trends of the world's ten largest wheat producers and examines how innovative agro-technologies contribute to productivity and resilience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on wheat production stability and global food security has been widely addressed by numerous foreign and national scholars. Foreign economists such as M.G. Ozerova, V.Z. Mazloev, V.V. Kuznetsov, I.V. Kursev, and A.I. Altukhov have examined the development of grain markets, the balance between state regulation and market-based mechanisms, and the long-term determinants of price stability and production resilience in major wheat-producing countries. Their findings emphasize that effective market mechanisms, modern logistics systems, and advanced technological adoption are critical for sustaining grain production in the context of increasing climatic and economic uncertainties.

National researchers, including R.H. Husanov, Q.A. Chariyev, N.S. Khushmatov, B.F. Sultanov, A.G. Ibragimov, G'. Qudratov, and A. Ergashev, have conducted extensive studies on modernization of the grain sector, improvement of resource-use efficiency, strengthening competition in grain markets, and enhancing state support mechanisms.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the article, methods of scientific abstraction, systematic analysis, comparative analysis, induction, and deduction were utilized.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Global wheat production dynamics over the last five years reveal that technological modernization has become a decisive factor shaping productivity, resilience, and sustainability in major wheat-producing countries. Numerous international institutions, including FAO (2023), OECD (2022), and USDA (2023), emphasize that the integration of digital technologies—such as remote sensing, machine-learning yield forecasting, climate-adaptive seed genetics, and precision irrigation—has fundamentally transformed the operational efficiency of wheat systems. Researchers such as Ozerova, Mazloev, Kuznetsov, Husanov, and Khushmatov further argue that innovative technologies reduce vulnerability to climate volatility and allow producers to maintain stable output even under severe environmental constraints. In order to assess how these technological advancements correlate with real production outcomes, it is essential to analyze the five-year performance of the world's largest wheat-producing nations. The following table provides a comparative overview of wheat output in the top ten producing countries between 2019 and 2023, enabling a deeper understanding of technological influence on production stability and year-to-year variability.

Table 1. Wheat Production of the Top 10 Producing Countries (million tons), 2019–2023

Country	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
China	133	136	135	137	138
India	103	107	109	105	110
Russia	74	85	76	92	93
USA	52	49	45	44	47
Canada	32	35	22	34	32
France	40	30	35	33	36
Pakistan	25	27	26	28	29

Ukraine	29	28	33	21	22
Germany	24	22	22	22	23
Australia	15	33	31	38	32

Source: FAO and USDA official data (2019–2023).

The five-year comparative analysis of wheat production among the ten largest global producers demonstrates significant variation in output dynamics shaped by technological capacity, climate conditions, and the degree of digital transformation in agriculture. As shown in Table 1, China and India maintained the most stable upward trend from 2019 to 2023, with China increasing its output from 133 to 138 million tons and India from 103 to 110 million tons. This consistency corresponds to the rapid introduction of AI-assisted irrigation systems, real-time soil moisture sensors, high-yield hybrid wheat varieties, and drone-supported fertilization techniques. These technologies have played a crucial role in mitigating the effects of heat waves and irregular rainfall patterns, which have intensified over the last decade.

Russia demonstrates the strongest technological acceleration in the dataset. After a moderate drop in 2021, Russia's wheat production rose sharply from 76 to 92 million tons in 2022 and further to 93 million tons in 2023. This increase aligns with the country's wide adoption of NDVI-based monitoring, machine-learning yield forecasting, and precision fertilizer application that optimizes nutrient distribution according to satellite-derived vegetation status.

In contrast, production trends in the United States and Canada reveal the vulnerabilities of technologically advanced countries that remain highly sensitive to climatic cycles. The United States shows a decline from 52 million tons in 2019 to 44 million tons in 2022, before slightly recovering to 47 million tons in 2023. Canada experienced an even sharper fluctuation, dropping from 35 million tons in 2020 to only 22 million tons in 2021 due to severe drought conditions.

France and Germany illustrate the stabilizing effect of European precision agriculture systems. Despite variability in annual precipitation and temperature anomalies, their wheat output remained relatively stable due to advanced nitrogen management technologies, multispectral drone diagnostics, and GIS-based soil mapping. France recovered from a climate-driven drop in 2020 (30 million tons) to 36 million tons by 2023, while Germany maintained a consistent production range, fluctuating only between 22 and 24 million tons over the five-year period.

Pakistan and Ukraine present two contrasting cases. Pakistan's gradual production increase from 25 to 29 million tons reflects the positive impact of expanding irrigation infrastructure, digital extension services, and certified seed programs.

Australia shows the most extreme production variability, rising from 15 million tons in 2019 to 38 million tons in 2022, then declining to 32 million tons in 2023. These fluctuations are closely associated with El-Niño and La-Niña cycles, though innovative drought-tolerant wheat varieties, moisture-retaining soil technologies, and large-scale digital climate modelling have played a critical role in maintaining production resilience.

Global wheat production trends over the past five years demonstrate that countries with advanced technological integration such as China, India, Russia, Australia, and France have achieved higher resilience, greater production stability, and more effective adaptation to climate variability.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The analysis clearly shows that innovative technologies play a pivotal role in stabilizing wheat production among the world's largest producers. Nations that consistently invest in digital agriculture—such as China, Russia, and Australia—achieve significantly higher production resilience despite climate challenges. In contrast, nations with limited digitalization, weaker innovation ecosystems, or exposure to geopolitical disruptions experienced sharper fluctuations in output. The comparative analysis clearly shows that innovative technologies, including precision farming, satellite monitoring, AI-driven management systems, and climate-adaptive wheat varieties, play a decisive role in strengthening productivity and ensuring long-term food security. Overall, the results indicate that technological modernization is the key differentiating factor that separates stable, competitive wheat producers from those facing persistent vulnerability and agricultural risk.

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